

PHENYL- α -NAPHTHYLAMINE-AZOBENZENE *p*-SULPHONIC ACID AS ADSORPTION INDICATOR

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A new adsorption indicator, phenyl- α -naphthylamine-azobenzene *p*-sulphonic acid has been suggested for argentometric titrations. It differs from all the classical adsorption indicators in having both acidic as well as basic character which makes it applicable both in the titrations of halide ions against silver ions as well as in the reverse titrations of silver ions against halide ions in which acidic and basic dyes respectively used to be employed separately. The adsorbability of the indicator, both by the positively as well as negatively charged silver halide bodies, endows it with a sharp colour change at the end-point, a ready reversibility and a large range of applicability in the argentometric titrations.

In a recent communication from these laboratories (Mehrotra, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1948, 2, 36), the author has described the applicability of congo red as adsorption indicator in argentometric titrations. This indicator essentially differs from all other previously described adsorption indicators, because it combines within itself the properties of the acidic dyestuffs like phthaleins and basic dyes like rhodamines, and hence can be used in both the titrations in which the above classes of dyes have been separately employed. The present communication extends the study to another dye of the same type, viz., phenyl- α -naphthylamine-azobenzene *p*-sulphonic acid.

Phenyl- α -naphthylamine-azobenzene *p*-sulphonic acid exhibits a marked colour change from violet to red-orange in the p_H range of 3 to 5. On account of the presence of the acid sulpho group in the molecule, it was expected that the positively charged silver halide particles would adsorb the red-orange anions of the dye, but the negatively charged silver halide body would show a preferential adsorption of the violet cations of the dye. Thus it was expected that the indicator would mark the end-point in the titration of halide ions with silver ions by a colour change from violet-blue to red-orange on the particles, whereas in the reverse titrations, it would show the opposite colour change. However, in the neutral medium (p_H 7), the silver halide particles were found to show an irreversible adsorption for the red-orange anions of the dye, but the red coloured precipitate thus obtained exhibited a colour change which prompted further investigation. On adding a drop of dilute nitric acid to the red particles, they immediately took up a deep blue shade which again changed to red on the addition of a slight excess of ammonia on the particles. Therefore, the titrations were repeated in the p_H range of 3 to 5, and it was found that in this range, the dye was capable of indicating the end-point with very sharp and reversible colour change both in the titrations of halide ions against silver ions as well as in the reverse titrations of silver ions with halide ions.

EXPERIMENTAL

A B.D.H. sample of the dye, phenyl- α -naphthylamine-azobenzene *p*-sulphonic acid was recrystallised and its 0.2% solution used as adsorption indicator throughout these investigations.

The potassium chloride, bromide, iodide and thiocyanate and silver nitrate were taken of the B.D.H. AnalaR standard and their standard solutions were prepared by the well known methods.

Titration of Chloride Ions against Silver Ions and vice versa.—As stated above, when the titration of potassium chloride (about $N/10$) is carried out with silver nitrate (of about the same strength) with 8 to 10 drops of the indicator for every 10 c.c. of the chloride solution, the pink colour of the suspension does not show any colour change as silver nitrate solution is run in. However, as suggested by Fajans, the dye regulates the beginning of coagulation of the precipitate such that the coagulation of the suspension along with simultaneous adsorption of the dye occurs at the equivalent point. The end-point is quite sharp, but its usefulness is very much limited by its irreversible nature. However, if the p_H of the medium is regulated between 3 and 5, the coagulation of the precipitate occurs much earlier and the coagulated particles adsorb the dye with the development of blue colour on the particles. Just at the equivalent point, half a drop of the silver nitrate solution in excess turns the blue colour on the coagulated particles into a red shade. The end-point though occurring on the coagulated particles is quite reversible. The reversibility and the sharpness of the colour change can be augmented by the addition of 1 c.c. of 5% chloride-free dextrin solution per 10 c.c. of the chloride solution taken. Dextrin is a protective colloid and does not allow the precipitate to coagulate, and hence the colour change in its presence occurs in the colloidal phase. However, for a sharp colour change to occur, the p_H of the solution should be carefully controlled in the range of 3 to 5. If the p_H of the medium becomes too low, say 1 to 2, then the precipitate does not become red at the equivalent point, but remains blue and requires a sufficient (about 4 to 6%) excess of silver nitrate before the particles assume a red shade. On the other hand, if the p_H of the medium becomes higher than 5, then the blue colour on the particles does not appear and the end-point is similar to the one described in neutral medium.

In the reverse titration of silver ions with chloride ions, the coagulation of the particles occurs much earlier and also the adsorption of the dye with a red shade on the precipitate. As the equivalent point approaches, the red colour on the particles has a tendency to change to blue. Just at the equivalent point, the bluish red colour on the particles changes to a sharp blue with half a drop of the chloride solution. The colour change at the end-point becomes sharper if a few drops of the indicator solution are added again near the end-point. The end-point though occurring on the coagulated particles is very sharp and quite reversible; it can be further improved by the addition of a protective colloid like dextrin. The p_H of the medium must be within 3 to 5.

Titration of Bromide Ions against Silver Ions and vice versa.—In neutral solution, the titration of bromide ions also yields results just similar to those described for chloride ions. In the p_H range of 3 to 5, the coagulation of the precipitate occurs much earlier and the particles adsorb the dye with the development of a bluish green colour. Just at the equivalent point, half a drop of the silver nitrate solution changes the colour of the precipitate from bluish green to red. The colour change at the end-point is quite reversible and very sharp. The titration can be carried out with sharp end-point even when the titrating solutions have a dilution as low as $N/200$; the coagulation, however, does not occur in the more dilute solutions and the colour change is observed in the apparently homogeneous phase.

In the reverse titration of silver ions against bromide ions, the coagulation occurs much earlier and the particles adsorb the dye with the development of a bright red colour which changes sharply to blue at the equivalent point. Addition of a few drops of the indicator near the equivalent point makes the colour change at the end-point much sharper. In the more dilute solutions of the order of $N/100$, the silver bromide does not coagulate out and the colour change occurs in the suspension.

Titration of Thiocyanate Ions against Silver Ions and vice versa.—The thiocyanate ions when titrated against silver ions give results similar to those with bromide ions. When the titration of thiocyanate ions against silver ions is carried out in the p_H range of 3 to 5, colour change from bluish violet to pink occurs at the equivalent point. The titration can be carried out with sharp end-point up to a dilution of $N/100$. In the reverse titration, opposite colour change occurs on the coagulated particles.

Titration of Iodide Ions against Silver Ions and vice versa.—In the titration of iodide ions against silver ions in the p_H range of 3 to 5, coagulation occurs much earlier and the particles assume a greenish blue shade. Just at the equivalent point, the colour of the particles changes sharply to red. The colour change at the end-point is very sharp and quite reversible. The end-point remains very sharp even when the titrating solutions are as dilute as $N/500$. The reverse titrations of silver ions against iodide ions can be carried out with very sharp end-points indicated by a colour change from red to bluish green.

TABLE I

Vol. & conc. of halide soln.	Indicator (drops).	Vol. & conc. of $AgNO_3$ soln.	Transition of colour.	Detailed conditions.
$N/10$ -KCl, 10 c.c.	8	$N/10$, 9.98 to 10.02 c.c.	Violet pink susp → pink ppt.	Coagulation just at the end-point with transference of colour from suspension to ppt. End-point is sharp but irreversible.
$N/10$ -KCl, 10 c.c. + 2 to 4 c.c. of $N/500$ - HNO_3	8	$N/10$, 10 to 10.02 c.c.	Blue ppt. → pink ppt.	Coagulation occurs much earlier Colour change occurs on the coagulated particles. The end-point is very sharp and quite reversible. If titration is carried out in presence of a little dextrin, the colour change occurs in the suspension phase.
$N/10$ -KCNS, 10 c.c. + 2 to 4 c.c. $N/500$ - HNO_3	6	$N/10$, 10 to 10.02 c.c.	Violet blue ppt. → pink ppt.	Coagulation occurs much earlier. The colour change occurring on the coagulated particles is very sharp and quite reversible.
$N/100$ -KCNS, 10 c.c. + 2 to 4 c.c. $N/500$ - HNO_3	4	$N/100$, 10 to 10.04 c.c.	Violet blue susp. → pink susp.	The colour change occurring in the homogeneous suspension phase is quite sharp and reversible.
$N/10$ -KBr, 10 c.c. + 2 to 4 c.c. $N/500$ - HNO_3	8	$N/10$, 10 to 10.04 c.c.	Bluish green ppt. → pink ppt.	The colour change though occurring on coagulated particles is very sharp and quite reversible.
$N/100$ -KBr, 10 c.c. + 2 to 4 c.c. $N/500$ - HNO_3	6	$N/100$, 10 to 10.04 c.c.	Bluish susp. → pink susp.	Very sharp and reversible end-point occurring in the suspension phase.
$N/10$ -KI, 10 c.c. + 2 to 4 c.c. $N/500$ - HNO_3	8	$N/10$, 10 to 10.02 c.c.	Bluish green ppt. → pink ppt.	The end-point is very sharp and quite reversible.
$N/500$ -KI, 10 c.c. + 2 to 4 c.c. $N/500$ - HNO_3	4	$N/500$, 10 to 10.02 c.c.	Bluish susp. → pink susp.	The end-point occurs in the suspension phase and is very sharp and quite reversible.

TABLE II

Vol. & conc. of AgNO ₃ soln.	Indicator (drops).	Vol. & conc. of halide soln.	Transition of colour.	Detailed conditions.
N/10-AgNO ₃ , 10 c.c. + 2 to 5 c.c. of N/500-HNO ₃	4	9.98 to 10.02 c.c. of N/10-KCl or KCNS	Violet ppt. → blue ppt.	The coagulation occurs much earlier and the particles adsorb the dye with a pink shade. As the end-point approaches, the pink colour on the particles changes to violet. Just at the end-point, the particles change their shade from violet to blue. The end-point is very sharp and quite reversible. The colour change is made sharper by the addition of a few drops of the indicator near the end-point. Coagulation occurs much before the end-point. The colour change occurring on the coagulated particles is very sharp and quite reversible.
N/10-AgNO ₃ , 10 c.c. + 2 to 5 c.c. of N/500-HNO ₃	4	9.98 to 10.02 c.c. of N/10- KBr or KI	Violet pink ppt. → blue ppt.	
N/100-AgNO ₃ , 10 c.c. + 2 to 5 c.c. N/500- HNO ₃	4	9.98 to 10.0 c.c. of N/100-KBr	Pink susp. → blue susp.	The colour change occurs in the suspension phase and very sharp and quite reversible.
N/500-AgNO ₃ , 10 c.c. + 2 to 5 c.c. N/500- HNO ₃	4	9.98 to 10.00 c.c. of N/500-KI	Pink susp. → blue susp.	Same as above.

Mechanism of the Colour change at the End-point.—The colour change at the end-point can be easily explained by Fajan's views (*Z. Electrochem.*, 1923, 29, 495). The dye, phenyl- α -naphthylamine-azobenzene *p*-sulphonic acid has got both acidic as well as basic character and in presence of acids, it gives violet-blue cations and in the presence of alkalis, red anions. In the p_H range of 3 to 5, both the cations as well as the anions of the dye are present in equilibrium, and hence in this range of p_H , the particles of silver halide, which are positively charged in the presence of excess of silver ions, adsorb preferentially the red anions of the dye. The anions of the dye being removed by adsorption from the supernatant suspension, the equilibrium between the acidic and basic forms of the dye is disturbed. More anions are formed to maintain the equilibrium, and more are adsorbed on the particles of the precipitate until the adsorption of the dye in the form of red anions is almost complete. Thus, the adsorption of the dye by the silver halide bodies with the development of a red colour in the presence of an excess of silver ions is so easily explained. Similarly, the particles of the silver halide precipitate have got a negative charge in the presence of excess of halide ions, and hence they preferentially adsorb the violet-blue cations of the dye and thus develop a blue shade on their surface in the presence of excess of halide ions. The mechanism of the colour change occurring in the above titrations is thus simply explained on Fajan's theory.

Thanks are due to the Scientific Research Committee of the U. P. Government for a contingency grant which partly met the cost of chemicals used in the above investigation.